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The Relationship Between Primary School 4th Grade Students' Reader Self-Concept and Reading Comprehension Levels

İlkokul 4.Sınıf Öğrencilerinin Okur Benlik Algısı ile Okuduğunu Anlama Düzeyleri Arasındaki İlişki

ABSTRACT

The term "reader self-perception" is used to describe the individual's concept of themselves as a reader. It encompasses children's personal beliefs, attitudes, and observations pertaining to reading activities. The reader's self-concept is shaped by the interaction of three key factors: the child's perception of their own competence in the reading process, their perception of reading as either easy or difficult, and their attitudes towards reading. The objective of this study was to ascertain the relationship between fourth-grade primary school students' perceptions of their reading self and their reading comprehension levels. The research was conducted using a relational survey model. The study group consisted of 252 students, 120 female and 132 male, in the 4th grade of primary school in public schools in the Yenimahalle district of the Ankara province. The data were collected using two instruments: the Reading Comprehension Test, which was employed to assess the students' reading comprehension abilities, and the Reader Self-Perception Scale, which was utilized to ascertain their perceptions of reading. The data were analysed using the SPSS 22 package program. The data were analysed using a t-test, one-way ANOVA and Pearson correlation coefficient. The findings of the study indicated that there was a positive and moderate correlation between students' self-perception as readers and their reading comprehension abilities. In the study, the relationship between the sub-dimensions of the reader self-perception scale and reading comprehension was examined. The results revealed a statistically positive and moderate level of a significant relationship between the reading comprehension levels of primary school 4th grade students and the attitude, difficulty and competence sub-dimension scores. When the mean scores were considered, it was determined that female students exhibited a higher reading self-concept than their male counterparts.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Reader self-concept, Reading Comprehension, Primary School Students

ÖZET

Okur benlik algısı, okumaya yönelik benlik kavramını ifade eder. Çocukların okuma etkinliklerinde kendi inançları, tutumları ve gözlemlerini kapsar. Okur benliği, çocukların kendilerini okuma sürecinde yeterli hissetme, okumayı kolay ya da zor algılama ve okumaya yönelik tutumlarının etkileşimiyle şekillenir. Bu çalışmada, ilkököl 4.sınıf öğrencilerinin okur benlik algıları ve okuduğunu anlama düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin tespit edilmesi amaçlanmıştır. Araştırma ilişkisel tarama modelinde gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırmanın çalışma grubunu, Ankara ili Yenimahalle ilçesine bağlı devlet okullarında ilkököl 4. sınıflarında öğrenim gören 120 kız, 132 erkek olmak üzere toplam 252 öğrenci oluşturmaktadır. Veri toplama aracı olarak; öğrencilerin okuduğunu anlama becerilerini ölçmek için "Okuduğunu Anlama Testi" ve öğrencilerin okumaya yönelik algılarını belirlemek için ise "Okur Benlik Algısı Ölçeği" kullanılmıştır. Veriler SPSS 22 paket programı ile analiz edilmiştir. Verilerin analizinde t-testi, tek yönlü ANOVA ve Pearson korelasyon katsayısı kullanılmıştır. Araştırma sonucunda öğrencilerin okur benlik algısı ile okuduğunu anlama düzeyleri arasında pozitif yönde orta düzeyde bir ilişki olduğu ortaya konmuştur. Araştırmada okur benlik algısı ölçeğinin alt boyutları ile okuduğunu anlama arasındaki ilişki incelenmiş, ilkököl 4.sınıf öğrencilerinin okuduğunu anlama düzeyleri ile tutum alt boyutu, güçlük alt boyutu ve yetkinlik alt boyutu puanları arasında istatistiksel açıdan pozitif yönde orta düzeyde anlamlı bir ilişkinin olduğu ortaya konmuştur. Ortalama puanlar dikkate alındığında kız öğrencilerin okur benlik algılarının erkek öğrencilere göre daha yüksek olduğu sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

Keywords: Okur Öz Algısı, Okuduğunu Anlama, İlkokul Öğrencileri

1. INTRODUCTION

The term "self-concept" is used to describe an individual's perception and evaluation of themselves, as well as the beliefs and images that they consider to be true about themselves (Bal, 2006). The term "self-perception" is used to describe the concepts that an individual holds about themselves. This concept encompasses thoughts, beliefs and emotional responses pertaining to identity, capabilities, values, emotions and relationships. The term "self-perception" is used to describe the process of understanding, recognising and evaluating oneself. The formation of self-perception is frequently shaped by a multitude of external influences. Such factors may include childhood experiences, social interactions, cultural influences, life experiences and personal achievements. These factors influence the individual's perception of themselves, including their self-evaluations and emotional responses.

The concept of academic self-concept describes the manner in which an individual perceives themselves. This perception frequently manifests in observable behaviours rather than feelings, and is particularly concerned with perceptions of academic achievement, self-efficacy and competence. This concept is related not only to emotional constructs such as self-acceptance, self-worth or self-esteem, but also to the ability to evaluate one's own abilities and achievements (Doğan, et.al., 2005). The self-concepts that are formed in certain behaviours, particularly in areas such as mathematics and social studies, affect the subordinate self-concepts and come together to form the academic self-concept (Schunk, 2011).

The term "reader self-concept" is used to describe an individual's perception of themselves in relation to the act of reading. It encompasses children's personal beliefs, attitudes, and observations pertaining to reading activities (Wilson, et. al., 1995). The formation of the reader's self-concept is influenced by the interplay of three key factors: the child's perception of their own competence in the reading process, their subjective experience of reading as either straightforward or challenging, and their attitudes towards reading itself (Chapman & Tunmer, 1997). The extant research demonstrates that children who define themselves as good readers are successful in employing effective reading strategies, are successful in coping with reading difficulties and are more effective in constructing meaning (Henk & Melnick, 1995). Conversely, children who did not consider themselves to be proficient readers were observed to exhibit greater reluctance and inattentiveness during the reading process (Henk, et. al., 2012).

One of the principal objectives of reading instruction is to enhance students' comprehension abilities. Reading comprehension can be defined as the process of deriving meaning from a written text. For this reason, it is one of the fundamental language skills that students at the primary education level are expected to acquire (Rose & Di, 2000). Reading comprehension can be defined as the creation of a mental structure through the combination of the meanings derived from various mental processes, including examination, sorting, classification, association, questioning, and the evaluation of information obtained through reading in relation to the reader's prior knowledge (Güneş, 2009). Reading comprehension can be defined as the process of integrating the reader's prior knowledge and experiences with the content and relationships of the text. This entails interacting with the text and constructing meaning (Pardo, 2004, p. 272).

The acquisition of reading comprehension skills for students represents a crucial step in the eradication of numerous issues inherent to the learning process. The reading and comprehension skills acquired by students during their primary school years have a significant impact on their future academic and professional success. Given that reading comprehension forms the basis of all courses, students who demonstrate proficiency in this area are likely to achieve academic success. Conversely, students with low reading comprehension skills tend to experience significant academic challenges.

In a study conducted by Esmer (2019), the effects of postmodern texts on the comprehension skills of students in the fourth grade of primary school were evaluated, as part of an examination of recent studies on reader self-perception. The objective of this study was to examine the direct and indirect relationships between oral and silent fluent reading, reader self-perception, reading engagement, and response to text levels. Furthermore, studies on the development and adaptation of scales were also identified in other research on related topics (Yaylı & Duru, 2008; Yıldız & Bulut, 2016; Wigfield & Guthrie, 1997). In the study conducted by Altunkaya (2018), the relationship between eighth-grade students' perceptions of reading self-efficacy and their reading comprehension levels was examined. In the study conducted by Baştuğ and Çelik (2015), the reader self-perception levels of secondary school students were examined according to the variables of gender, grade level, student and family reading frequencies, and choice of reading environments. The objective of this study was to examine the relationship between fourth grade primary school students' reader self-perception and reading comprehension levels. In alignment with this objective, four sub-objectives were identified:

1. Does a significant relationship exist between the scores obtained by fourth-grade primary school students on the Reader Self-Perception Scale and their scores on the Reading Comprehension Test?
2. Does a relationship exist between the scores obtained by fourth-grade primary school students on the Reader Self-Perception Scale and their reading comprehension scores?
3. Does there exist a significant difference at the scores of fourth-grade primary school students on the Reader Self-Perception Scale according to gender?
4. Does there exist a significant difference at Reading Comprehension Test scores between male and female students in the fourth grade of primary school?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Design

The objective of this research is to provide a descriptive account of the existing situation. Accordingly, the research was conducted in accordance with the relational survey model, which is one of the survey models. Relational survey models are research models that seek to identify changes in the relationship between two or more variables (Karasar, 2013). He research does not involve any intervention or action. Given the objective of the research, a descriptive survey was deemed the most appropriate research model. The present study examined the correlation between students' perceptions of their reading abilities and their actual reading comprehension levels.

2.2. Study Group

The sample group for this study, which was conducted to investigate the relationship between reading self-concept and reading comprehension levels among fourth-grade primary school students, was selected through convenience sampling from a population of 252 students enrolled in public schools in the Yenimahalle district of Ankara province during the 2023-2024 academic year. Descriptive data pertaining to the sample group are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Data on the Sample Group

Grade Level	Female		Male		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
4th Grade	120	48	132	52	252	100

A breakdown of the data reveals that 52% of the sample group were male students and 48% were female students. The research was conducted with a total of 252 students.

2.3. Data Collection Instruments

Two data collection tools were used to collect the data. The first one is the Reader Self-Perception Scale. The second data collection tool is the Reading Comprehension Test.

The Reader Self-Perception Scale: is a tool designed to assess an individual's self-perception in relation to their reading abilities. The Reader Self-Perception Scale, originally developed by Chapman and Tunmer (1995), was subsequently adapted into Turkish by Yıldız and Bulut (2016) for the purpose of determining students' perceptions of themselves as readers. The scale, which can be applied from the first to the fourth grades of primary school, has a three-dimensional structure consisting of 10 items, namely competence, difficulty and attitude. The scale is based on a 5-point Likert scale, with the following responses: 1 = no, never; 2 = no, not usually; 3 = undecided; 4 = yes, usually; 5 = yes, always. The correlation analysis conducted between the sub-dimensions of the developed reader self-perception scale revealed significant correlations between the 'competence factors' ($r = .88$), 'attitude factors' ($r = .75$) and 'difficulty factors' ($r = .89$). The correlation analysis revealed significant correlations between the competence factor and both the attitude factor ($r = .60$) and the difficulty factor ($r = .63$). Furthermore, a notable correlation was identified between the attitude factor and the difficulty factor ($r = .52$). The results demonstrate a significant interrelationship between the sub-dimensions of the reader self-perception scale. The reliability of the scale was determined through the calculation of the Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient, which yielded a value of .86.

Reading comprehension test: In the study, the Reading Comprehension Test developed by Bulut and Yıldız (2021) was used to determine students' reading comprehension levels. In the item analysis of the prepared reading comprehension test at the end of the pilot study, the difficulty and discrimination indices of each item were calculated. According to these indices, 20 of the appropriate questions were included in the reading comprehension test.

Table 2. Reading Comprehension Test Item Difficulties, Item Discrimination and Reliability Coefficients

Text Type	Item no.	Item discrimination index	Item difficulty index	Measurement reliability of the test
Narrative text	Question 1	.34	.36	.72
	Question 2	.34	.44	
	Question 3	.34	.44	
	Question 4	.41	.71	
	Question 5	.42	.51	
	Question 6	.36	.63	
	Question 7	.53	.76	
	Question 8	.34	.40	
	Question 9	.38	.50	
	Question 10	.26	.57	
Informative text	Question 1	.33	.41	.79
	Question 2	.33	.37	
	Question 3	.33	.56	
	Question 4	.25	.54	
	Question 5	.33	.50	
	Question 6	.37	.56	
	Question 7	.37	.39	
	Question 8	.41	.51	
	Question 9	.37	.60	
	Question 10	.33	.62	

Table 2 presents data regarding the item difficulties, item discrimination, and reliability coefficients of the test items. Upon analysis of the discrimination coefficients of the items, it was observed that all items exhibited a value exceeding 0.20. In order to evaluate the reliability of the measurement, the Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient method was employed in the reading comprehension test. The results of the analysis yielded a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.72 for the narrative text and 0.79 for the informative text. The aforementioned values demonstrate that the measurements of both texts are reliable.

2.4. Data Collection Process

The data for this study, which examines the relationship between fourth grade primary school students' reading self-concept and reading comprehension levels, were collected in person by the researchers from four different schools in the Yenimahalle district of Ankara province during the autumn term of the 2023-2024 academic year. The research was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards set forth by the Kastamonu University Ethics Committee. The necessary permissions for the application were duly obtained. During the data collection process, the students were interviewed in person, and participation in the study was on a voluntary basis. Prior to the administration of the scale, preliminary inquiries were posed to ascertain the participants' comprehension of the scale's application form.

2.5. Data Analysis

The present study aims to examine the relationship between students' reader self-perception and their reading comprehension levels. To this end, the Reader Self-Perception Scale and the Reading Comprehension Test were applied to a total of 252 students. The data were subsequently transferred to the SPSS 21 package programme. The data were analysed using the SPSS 21 package programme. In order to facilitate comparison between the two instruments, the lowest score that can be obtained from the scale (1) was determined as the highest score (5), and the highest score that can be obtained from the reading comprehension test was determined as (100). The study's data were analysed to ascertain whether they exhibited a normal distribution, with the skewness and kurtosis values employed for this purpose. The skewness and kurtosis coefficient values fall within the range of -1 and +1, indicating that the scores exhibit a normal distribution.

Table 3. Normality Test Data Related to Students' Reading Self-Perception and Reading Comprehension Scores

Values	N	Min.	Max.	M	SS	Skewness	Kurtosis
Reader self-perception	252	1	5	3,88	,67	-,48	,32
Reading comprehension test	252	0	100	74,81	14,62	-,52	,13

Upon analysis of Table 3, it becomes evident that the skewness and kurtosis coefficient values for the reader self-perception scale fall within the range of -1 to +1. It is acknowledged that the kurtosis and skewness values for the reading comprehension test fall within the range of -1 to +1. The results of the analysis demonstrate that the scores of the students' reading self-perception and reading comprehension tests exhibit a normal distribution. Consequently, an independent t-test was employed in the data analysis to ascertain the correlation between gender variables. Furthermore, Pearson's product-moment correlation

coefficient was employed to ascertain the relationship between reader self-perception and reading comprehension scores. Furthermore, frequency, percentage and mean scores were employed to describe the data.

3. (FINDINGS)

The initial step was to examine the correlation between the Reader Self-Concept Scale scores of fourth-grade primary school students and their Reading Comprehension Test scores. The findings are presented in the table below. As evidenced in Table 4, the data revealed a statistically positive and moderately significant correlation between fourth-grade primary school students' reading self-concept scale scores and reading comprehension scores ($r = .667$, $p < .01$).

Table 4. The Correlation Between Students' Reader Self-Concept and Reading Comprehension Scores

Variable	N	r	p
Reader self-perception score	252	,667	,00
Reading comprehension test score			

$p < .01$

The results demonstrate a linear relationship between reading self-concept and reading comprehension levels among fourth-grade primary school students. In other words, the results demonstrate that as students' perceptions of their reading abilities increase, their reading comprehension levels also increase. Conversely, as these perceptions decrease, reading comprehension levels also decrease.

Table 5. The Correlation Between Students' Reading Comprehension Scores and Sub-Dimensions of Reader Self-Perception

Variable	N	r	p
Reading comprehension score-attitude	252	,388	,00
Reading comprehension score-difficulty	252	,450	,00
Reading comprehension score-competence	252	,473	,00

$p < .01$

The data in Table 5 revealed a statistically positive and moderately significant relationship between the reading self-concept scale attitude sub-dimension scores of fourth grade primary school students and their reading comprehension scores ($r = .388$, $p < .01$). Furthermore, a similar relationship was observed between the difficulty sub-dimension scores and reading comprehension scores ($r = .450$, $p < .01$), as well as between the competence sub-dimension scores and reading comprehension scores ($r = .473$, $p < .01$).

Table 6. T-Test Results of Reader Self-Perception Scale Scores According to Gender

Gender	N	M	SS	sd	t	p
Male	132	3,77	0,78	250	-2,556	,011
Female	120	4,00	0,57			

$p < .05$

The data presented in the table indicates a statistically significant difference in the scores of fourth-grade primary school students on the reader self-perception scale according to gender ($t(250) = -2.556$, $p < .05$). This finding indicates a significant discrepancy between the reader self-perceptions of male and female students. The results demonstrated that the reader self-perception of female students ($M = 4.00$) was higher than that of male students ($M = 3.77$).

Table 7. T-Test Results of Reading Comprehension Test Scores According to Gender

Gender	N	M	SS	sd	t	p
Male	132	71,96	15,11	250	-3,081	,00
Female	120	77,66	14,14			

$p < .01$

The data in the table indicates a statistically significant difference in reading comprehension test scores between male and female 4th grade primary school students ($t(250) = -3.081$, $p < .01$). This finding indicates a significant discrepancy in reading comprehension levels between male and female students. The results demonstrated that the reading comprehension levels of female students ($M = 77.66$) were higher than those of male students ($M = 71.96$).

Table 8. Descriptive Data Related to the Items of Reader Self-Perception Scale

Statements	Mean	SS
Do you like playing word games in class (crossword puzzles, hangman)?	4,54	,94
Can you correct your mistakes while reading?	4,48	,79
Do you like to read at home?	4,45	,91
Do you like reading to yourself?	4,41	,92
Is it easy for you to read?	4,39	,90
Do you feel good when you read something?	4,32	,86
Do you think you read well?	4,29	,86
Is reading fun for you?	4,28	,95
Are you interested in reading?	4,25	,97
Do you like to read to your mum and dad?	4,23	,95
Do you like reading stories with lots of words?	4,08	1,09
Would you like to read in class?	4,01	1,08
Can you deduce the meaning of a story you read on your own?	3,93	,89
Can you decode the sounds in words on your own?	3,92	1,11
Are you looking forward to reading it?	3,92	1,11
Can you quickly learn what you read?	3,88	,94
Are you good at remembering words?	3,88	1,12
Does reading make you unhappy?	3,84	1,32
Do you find the books you read in class difficult?	3,82	1,04
Can you understand difficult words in a story on your own, even without pictures?	3,81	1,72
Is it difficult for you to read to your friends in class?	3,66	1,52
Do you feel inadequate while reading?	3,56	1,52
Do you need additional help when reading?	3,55	1,58
Do you find it difficult to understand the stories you read in class?	3,55	1,65
Do you make a lot of mistakes when you read?	3,54	1,57
Do you think it's easy to read words you've just seen?	3,42	1,16
Do other children in your class read more difficult words than you do?	3,19	1,49
Do your classmates read better than you?	3,18	1,45
Can you recognise the meaning of an unfamiliar word when you read it?	3,06	1,22
If you can't say a word, do you get help?	2,98	1,43

A review of the data in Table 8 reveals that students' perceptions of engaging in word games in the classroom are markedly positive, with an average rating of 4.54 on a 5-point scale. This finding indicates that the incorporation of games into the reading process in reading-oriented practices can influence students' perceptions of themselves as readers. Additionally, the data indicate that students perceive the correction of errors during the reading process to be a highly effective strategy (4.48). Furthermore, the students expressed a positive attitude towards reading in both school and home environments. They found reading to be a straightforward and enjoyable activity.

It is evident that students exhibit a low level of perception regarding the seeking of assistance from others when encountering difficulties in the reading process (2.98). Furthermore, it was established that the students did not consider themselves proficient in deducing the meaning of an unknown word while reading (3.06). Furthermore, the students' perceptions regarding the reading of new words encountered (3.42) were also found to be low.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicate that there is a positive and moderate correlation between students' perceptions of their reading abilities and their actual reading comprehension levels. Upon examination of the literature, it was found that the results of the study conducted by Aktaş and Ergül (2023) were consistent with those of the present study. In their study, Aktaş and Ergül (2023) demonstrated a positive correlation between students' reader self-perception and reading comprehension. Similarly, the study conducted by Baştuğ and Çelik (2015) reached the conclusion that there is a positive relationship between the reader self-perception of secondary school students and their reading comprehension. Bailey (2009) and Phillips (2002) demonstrated that there is a significant positive relationship between students' reader self-perception and reading comprehension. Conversely, Kwon and Linderholm (2014) established that students' self-perception of reading is a predictor of their metacognitive comprehension levels. The aforementioned results collectively indicate that an enhancement in students' reading self-perception is accompanied by an analogous increase in their reading comprehension level. In light of the aforementioned findings, it is imperative that relevant stakeholders incorporate studies that bolster students' reader self-perception into the learning process.

In the study, the relationship between the sub-dimensions of the reader self-perception scale and reading comprehension was examined. The results revealed a statistically positive and moderately significant relationship between the reading comprehension levels of primary school 4th grade students and their attitude, difficulty, and competence sub-dimension scores. In their study, Aktaş and Ergül (2023) identified a significant difference in the difficulty and competence sub-dimensions of reading comprehension and reader self-perception, but no significant difference in the attitude sub-dimension. This outcome may be attributed to the characteristics of the sample population with regard to the application in question.

The present study examined the relationship between reading self-concept and reading comprehension levels of fourth-grade primary school students. The findings revealed that, when the average scores were taken into consideration, the reading self-concept of female students was higher than that of male students. A review of the literature reveals studies in which female students report higher levels of reading self-perception (Aktaş & Ergül, 2023; Baştuğ & Çelik, 2015; İnnalı & Aydın, 2014; Meece et al., 2006; Ünal, 2012; Yaylı & Duru, 2008).

Once more, an examination of the literature reveals that female students exhibit a high self-perception of their reading abilities, which influences their attitudes towards reading (Karakoç, 2005), their motivation levels (Wigfield & Guthrie, 1997) and the extent to which they engage in reading activities (Gönen, et. al., 2004; Keleş, 2006). It can be reasonably assumed that students with high reading motivation also have more reading habits and allocate more time to reading.

Another noteworthy finding is that students hold highly positive perceptions of engaging in word games within the classroom setting. This finding indicates that the incorporation of games into the reading process in reading-oriented practices can facilitate students' perceptions of themselves as readers. Upon examination of the relevant literature, Varan and Sulak (2018) concluded that the implementation of vocabulary instruction through the use of educational games proved to be an effective approach for fostering the growth of students' mental vocabulary. The findings of this study align with those of Varan and Sulak (2018). In this framework, the implementation of vocabulary teaching activities through games plays a pivotal role in fostering students' reader self-perceptions towards reading.

Another finding from the study indicates that students' perceptions of seeking help from others when they cannot pronounce a word during the reading process are very low. This suggests that students are hesitant to ask for help from either their classmates or teachers. Additionally, it was found that students do not feel confident in inferring the meaning of unfamiliar words while reading. Moreover, their perceptions regarding reading newly encountered words are also at a low level.

In summary, this study revealed a moderate positive relationship between students' reader self-concept and their reading comprehension levels. The relationship between the sub-dimensions of the reader self-concept scale and reading comprehension was examined, and it was found that there is a statistically significant moderate positive correlation between the reading comprehension levels of 4th-grade primary school students and the scores of the attitude, difficulty, and competence sub-dimensions. Considering the average scores, it was concluded that the reader self-concepts of female students are higher than those of male students. Another finding from the study showed that students' perceptions of playing word games in class are very high. Additionally, it was observed that students' perceptions of seeking help when they cannot pronounce a word during the reading process are very low. Furthermore, students do not feel confident in inferring the meaning of unfamiliar words while reading, and their perceptions of reading newly encountered words are also low.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the relationship between the reading self-perception and reading comprehension levels of 4th-grade elementary school students was examined. Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations are provided:

- A moderate positive correlation was found between students' reading self-perception and their reading comprehension levels. Teachers could, therefore, focus more on activities that enhance students' reading self-perception to improve their reading comprehension skills.
- The study revealed that female students have higher reading self-perception than male students. Activities aimed at increasing reading self-perception, particularly for male students, could be developed and implemented.
- The results indicated that students have a high perception of word games. Teachers might consider incorporating more word games both inside and outside the classroom based on this finding.

- It was found that students are hesitant to seek help when they struggle with pronouncing words. Therefore, activities that encourage students to seek help in these situations could be implemented.
- The study identified that students have a low perception of reading new words. Teachers could conduct additional activities to address this issue.
- The research was conducted in the Yenimahalle district of Ankara. The study could be extended to a larger sample group by including more participants.
- The study employed a correlational survey model. Future research could explore this topic through experimental and mixed-method designs.

Limitations

This research has some limitations. The data were collected from three schools located in the Yenimahalle district of Ankara. The findings of the research are based on the data gathered from these three schools. Additionally, the study is limited to 4th-grade elementary school students.

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